

1 **Amigo3 marks young HSC while Amigo1 and Amigo2 mark aged HSC.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Citations

8 1. Kuja-Panula, J., Kiiltomäki, M., Yamashiro, T., Rouhiainen, A. and Rauvala, H., 2003. AMIGO, a
9 transmembrane protein implicated in axon tract development, defines a novel protein family with
10 leucine-rich repeats. *The Journal of cell biology*, 160(6), pp.963-973.

11 2. Soto, F., Tien, N.W., Goel, A., Zhao, L., Ruzycski, P.A. and Kerschensteiner, D., 2019. AMIGO2
12 scales dendrite arbors in the retina. *Cell reports*, 29(6), pp.1568-1578.